

INTERACTION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT AND EDUCATION-UPBRINGING

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Annotation: The Science of psychology, based on modern doctrine, traces the composition of the human personality mainly to the influence of three factors on the basis of evidence. Of them;

- the first is the influence of the external social environment in which a person is born and raised;
- the second is the influence of Education, which is regularly given to a person for a long period of time;
- the third is the influence of hereditary traits, which are given to a person in an innate, ready-made way.

This article discusses the changes in child education as well as the fact that education and upbringing are inextricably linked, and the methods of proper education in the upbringing of a child.

Keywords: Psychology, man, perfect man, upbringing, education, social attitude, the essence of the personality, psychic development, sensitive periods.

It is known that each person grows up living among people, grows up, is formed in a specific, in others, in a social environment that is not exactly repeated, in a specific social relationship, that is, in a family, community and society.

It is in social relations that a person participates as a member of society, as a manifestation of a certain class, one or another social group, and, finally, as an active member of certain communities with different levels of externality and organization.

The essence of the personality is social in terms of its nature. All mental properties in the individual, the sources of development of creative activity are in the social environment around him, in society. A person's personality is in causal dependence and is determined by his social marriage. In this sense, the development of the individual consists of the process of acquiring the social experience that arises in a relationship with people. As a result of this, the psychic characteristics, moral qualities, character, volitional qualities, interests, beliefs and worldview of a person are formed.

The environment, education and upbringing aimed at a certain goal, not only the conditions for the manifestation of something that has long been given, genetically strictly defined, but also the content of human psychic properties.

In this regard, firstly, a person is not a passive object under the influence of the environment, but an active being, therefore, life conditions, external influence do not define the human psyche, but are determined through the interaction of a person with the environment, through his activity in the environment. For this reason, it is advisable to talk not about the influence of the environment, but about the active interaction of a person with the surrounding environment.

Secondly, the development of the psyche ultimately depends on external conditions, external influences. But this development cannot be directly caused by external circumstances and external circumstances. These conditions as well as situations always affect a person's life experience, his personality, individual psychological characteristics and through the psychic qnyofa.

Thirdly, a person, as an active being, can also consciously change his personality, that is, engage in self-education, but this process occurs not in isolation from the environment, but in alignment with the environment and in interaction with the environment.

Summing up the above, we can say that the socially External found and active activity of a person (child, student) is the basis, tool and condition for his psychic development.

It goes without saying that for the psychic development of a person, natural, biological capabilities are extremely necessary. In order for human psychic properties to be contained in moderation, it is imperative to have a certain level of biological structure, the human brain and the nervous system. These natural properties are not just the forces, factors that cause the development of the psyche, but only the initial conditions.

Despite the fact that natural properties are not the force that brings progress to action, humanity has an impact on the development of the psyche.

First of all, natural properties determine various ways and methods of development of psychic properties. The characteristics of the human nervous system do not determine what psychic characteristics of the self-personality hych is, Hych a child of one norm is not born courageous or timid, strong-willed or weak-willed, hardworking or sloth, disciplined or undisciplined, if upbringing is properly External, all socially valuable qualities of character can be formed in the nervous system. For example, it will be possible to educate the personality of sabot-fortitude and self-control both in children with severe nervous system type, or in children with nervous system type calm. However, the first case will be more difficult to raise children than the second. In both cases, the ways and methods of educating the necessary qualities will be different.

Secondly, natural characteristics can also affect the level of a person's achievements in an area. For example, there are innate individual differences in ability. For this reason, some people excel in terms of the possibility of acquiring a certain activity from other people. And in some, on the contrary, they can lag behind them in terms of the possibility of acquiring one type of activity. In this sense, people do not have the opportunity to develop their abilities more than once. Although natural skills are of certain importance for the psychic development of students (for this reason, in the educational process, for example, some students are required to give more - excellent than other students, some students are given more effort by the teacher, pay attention and devote more time), these skills themselves do not play a decisive role in psychic development.

Psychologists with different orientations are discussing the problem of their interaction between education and upbringing on the one hand, and development on the other.

Under development, usually both types of phenomena are understood, and these concepts are closely related to each other: 1) biological, organic maturation of the brain, its maturation in terms of anatomical and physiological structure; 2) certain levels of growth of psychic (mental) development in quality, psychic development in the quality of specific mental maturation, by itself, mental development is associated with the biological solution of However, it cannot be said that the organic maturation of brain tumors occurs on the basis of

its own strictly biological laws, absolutely not tied to the environment, education. Environment, education and appropriate exercise contribute to the organic maturation of the brain structure.

What position does education have in this process? Does education perform a leading function in relation to development or vice versa? The solution to this problem determines the content and methodology of the educational process, the content of educational programs and textbooks.

In this regard, the German psychologist V.Shtern: it was he who pushed forward the idea that education goes after psychic development and adapts to it. Contrary to this opinion, the Russian psychologist L.S.Vygotsky was the first to put forward the rule that education and upbringing have a leading role in the development of the child's psyche, clearly expressing that education is ahead of development and takes him after it. In accordance with the first thought described above, Education uses only what is achieved by development therefore, it is necessary not to interfere in the process of mental maturation, not to interfere with it, but to wait passively until the opportunity for education is reached.

Swiss psychologist J.Piaget's theory is also permeated with these ideas.

J.Piaget believes that the mental growth of a child, going to develop based on his internal laws, goes through a series of genetic stages that are qualitatively specific. Education is the ability to only slightly speed up or slow down the process of mental maturation, but it cannot seriously affect how he reacts to the process of mental maturation. So education must be buyunnd by the laws of development. For example, it is useless for a child to teach him to think logically without the maturation of logical thinking. This is due to the fact that different stages of Education depend regardless of the specific age at which the corresponding psychological capabilities of the child ripen.

It should be noted that education plays a leading role, while education and development are interconnected; they are not two processes that occur separately, but a whole process that cannot be a complete mental development without education. Education is an impetus for development, followed by development. At the birth of the necessary conditions, education composes the skills of logical thinking and becomes the basis for appropriate mental development, but, simultaneously with the motivation for development, education itself relies on development, necessarily taking into account the characteristics of the achieved level of development, internal rules of development. Although the possibilities of his education are very wide, but not endless. Major Russian psychologist L.S.Vygotsky approaches the problem of education and development from the point of view of the socio-historical process, arguing that the assimilation of knowledge is a process of participation in the culture created in the development of the history of mankind. According to the cultural-historical theory of the development of psychic functions, which he applied to olga, psychic activity progress is understood as the acquisition of its "cultural" form, referring to the first external, then internal expression with various signs, directly reconstructing its "natural" form.

In this regard, L.S.The concept of "the closest zone of psychic development", which Vygotsky introduced into psychology, is of great importance. The essence of this is that the child's independent activity is carried out in cooperation with an adult, under his leadership. L.S.The concept of the "nearest zone of Psychic Development" introduced by Vygotsky provides an opportunity to understand the obvious content of the general rule "education goes ahead of progress,

E.Thorndike and J.Despite piaje's explanation of progress with education as the same thing L.S.Vigotsky:".Child Development hych mahal cannot be considered a shadow outside of school education," emphasizes. In addition, psychologists in the direction that education and progress are processes that are not subject to each other are also strongly criticized by him. P.P.Blonsky attaches particular importance to the place of education in the development of the child, therefore emphasizes that the mental development of students directly depends on the content of the school program. In his opinion-in the process of education, children get used to activities according to a certain rule. As a result of the influence of education, students experience control over self-and their own mental activity. Psychologist from scientists V.V.Davidov, P.Ya.Galperin, D.B.Elkanin, N.AMenchinskaya, A.A.Lyublinskaya, E.G.In their research, the gozievs emphasize the leading role of education in development.

Even if the factors and conditions of psychic development are determined, the sources of changes that occur in the psyche, the question of what are the forces that cause the development of the psyche in motion, is natural.

The forces that bring movements to the child's mental development are complex and diverse. The essence of development consists in the struggle of contradictions, internal contradictions between the forces that directly drive the development of the child, the psyche, the contradictions between old age and novelty that arise and are eliminated in the process of education and upbringing. Such conflicts include, for example, conflicts between the new needs generated by the activity and the possibilities of satisfying them; and with the growing physical and mental capabilities of the child, conflicts between the forms of interaction and types of activity that are formed; conflicts between the increased demands on the part of society, the team, large people from day to day and this level of mental development break.

For example, in a small school-age student there is a conflict between the readiness for independent volitional activity and the dependence of behavior on the current situation or directly on internal experiences while in adolescents the strongest conflicts are on the one hand between his self, self-assessment and the level of his own demands and, on the other hand, his inner Also, the inner experience of his real position in the team appears between the need to participate in the life of large people as a full-fledged member and the incompatibility of his capabilities with this.

All the conflicts that have been shown are eliminated by composing a somewhat higher level of psychic activity. As a result, the child rises to a higher stage of mental development. The need is satisfied-the conflict disappears. But the need that is satisfied, creates a new need. This conflict is replaced by another conflict, progress continues.

Development consists not only in the process of pure quantitative changes, that is, in the reproduction or reduction of some kind of psychic phenomena, properties and qualities, but also in connection with the emergence of qualitatively new properties, that is, newly formed qualities.

Psychologists note that there are general laws of psychic development. However, in relation to the influence of the environment, these laws are secondary, since the peculiarities of these laws depend on life circumstances, activity and upbringing. Here to such general laws first of all the unevenness of the development of the psyche breaks. The essence of this is that in any conditions, even in the most extreme conditions of education and upbringing, various mental signs, functions and characteristics of the individual do not stop at a single level of development. In some age periods of a child, extremely favorable conditions arise for

development in one direction or another of the psyche, and some of these conditions are of a temporary, fleeting nature. Such Age periods, which are the most favorable conditions for the development of one or another psychic characteristics and qualities, are called sensitive periods. The existence of such a sensitive period is caused by both the organically matured legitimacy of the brain, and certain psychic processes and properties, and life experience

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